

Review Article

"G-D's Physics" Complete Unification of Quantum & Relativistic Models, The Four Basic Physical Features & Resolution of the "Hubble's Tension Enigma"!

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RJMP's Announcement: "AN INTERNATIONAL CONTEST FOR VALIDATION OF 'G-D'S PHYSICS' 'UNCIARE-JRH' CRITICAL PREDICTION & RESOLUTION OF THE 'HUBBLE'S TENSION' ENIGMA"!

The current (breakthrough) article is associated with RJMP's International Contest for Validation of "G-D's Physics" 'UNCIARE-JRH' Critical Prediction & Resolution of 'Hubble's Tension's' Enigma": It calls Astronomers to submit an application for this International Contest aimed at empirically validating "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction which involves a precise* Astronomical measurement of UNCIARE-JRH's Critical Prediction of an increase in the current Astronomical Value of the Universe's Expansion Rate, i.e., by a "Minute Annual Increase" (MAI) of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc that will occur in the upcoming JRH: Oct. 3rd-4th, 2024, relative to such MAI* (precision measurement sensitivity) of the current rate of the universe's expansion (and will carry through until the next JRH: Sep. 22nd-23rd, 2025 – in which another MAI of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc will be added to the universe's accelerated rate of expansion!) Submissions (& Queries) regarding this International Contest should be directed to Dr. Bentovish's (Bentwich) e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com

Abstract

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics is currently undergoing a "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm", based upon direct empirical validation of two of "G-D's Physics" unique "Critical Predictions" as more valid than the corresponding GRT's & QM's predictions. Significantly, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm is anchored in it's discovery of a (novel) singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") which is shown capable of completely unifying between GRT & QM, as well as between the Four basic Physical Features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") and resolving both the "Gravitational Enigma" and "Hubble's Tension". A Call for Astronomers to validate JRH UNCIARE Critical Prediction's increase in universe's expansion rate during the JRH's Oct. 3-4th 2024 CHCF is made through a precise* Astronomical measurement of UNCIARE-JRH's Critical Prediction of an increase in the current Astronomical Value of the Universe's Expansion Rate, i.e., by a "Minute Annual Increase" (MAI) of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc that will occur in the upcoming JRH: Oct. 3rd-4th, 2024, relative to such MAI* (precision measurement sensitivity) of the current rate of the universe's expansion (and will carry through until the next JRH: Sep. 22nd-23rd, 2025 – in which another MAI of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc will be added to the universe's accelerated rate of expansion!) Queries regarding this empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction should be directed to Dr. Bentovish's (Bentwich) e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com. See also RJMP's Announcement: "An International Contest for Validation of G-D's Physics 'UNCIARE-JRH' Critical Prediction & Resolution of the Hubble's Tension' Enigma!"

Introduction

Most likely the greatest unresolved enigma in Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics is the principle theoretical inconsistency between General Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics – which is also closely related to the (unresolved) "Gravitational Enigma" (i.e., inability to unify between GRT's Gravitational Force and the Standard Model's other three fundamental Forces; alongside two other related "riddles": a) "Hubble's Tension"[32-35], i.e., an unexplained "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Rate of Expansion" ("CAGUARE", e.g., indicating an increase in the universe's rate of expansion over time)?! b) The existence of purely hypothetical "Dark Matter"[36], e.g., assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe – which yet failed to be detected experimentally

(despite over two full decades of intensive experimentations attempting to detect this "elusive" concept)?! It is no secret that (the great) Einstein himself devoted the entire second half of his illustrious scientific career in the pursuit after such a hypothetical "Unifying Field Theory" that could resolve this principle GRT-QM "theoretical inconsistency", as well as unify between those Four basic Physical Forces!

The basic Relativistic-Quantum "theoretical inconsistency" is anchored in a basic (apparent) contradiction between GRT's strict "Speed of Light Barrier" (SLB), that limits the transmission of any signal across space and time to the Speed of Light; which seems to be contradicted by QM's empirically validated "Quantum Entanglement" phenomenon indicating that

a measurement of one "entangled particles" "instantaneously" affects the measurement accuracy of another 'entangled particle's "complimentary value" (e.g., apparently violating the SLB strict limitation imposed by GRT)?! As noted above, this apparent Relativistic-Quantum "theoretical inconsistency" is also closely related to the Standard Model's inability to unify between its Three (integrated) Forces (e.g., Strong & Weak Nuclear Forces, Electromagnetic Force) – and the Gravitational Force (i.e., which is well explained by GRT)?! Yet another aspect of this "Gravitational Enigma" are its two interrelated "riddles" of a) "Hubble's Tension"³²⁻³⁵; and b) The hypothetical "Dark Matter"³⁶ (assumed to account for the accelerated expansion of the universe and comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe but yet cannot be detected or verified experimentally for the past twenty years?!)

However, such a "state of affairs" in Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics, in which:

- a) The two primary "pillars" of GRT & QM seem "inconsistent"?
- b) "Dark-Matter": Up to 95% of all the mass in the universe cannot be detected?
- c) The Universe's accelerated rate of expansion, e.g., including the unexplained "CAGUARE" phenomenon, or "Hubble's Tension"?
- d) Inability to unify between those Four basic Physical Features?

can be characterized as constituting a fundamental "Paradigmatic Crisis" of Twenty-First Century Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm, as analyzed by Kuhn³¹! According to Kuhn's³¹ (well-accepted) analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions"⁵⁰, in order for Science to accept such a "Paradigmatic-Shift" (in any given scientific sub-discipline), it is necessary for a few specific conditions to be fulfilled:

1) Existence of "Theoretical-inconsistencies" found in the Old "Standard Paradigm" (as indicated above).

2) The Existence of a Major "Unexplained" "Hubble-Tension" Phenomenon & Associated Purely Hypothetical "Dark-Matter" & "Dark-Energy" (DM/DE) Concepts?!

The "Major Unexplained Phenomenon" which cannot be accounted for by the Old MCR of GRT & QM are the purely hypothetical "DM/DE" concepts – which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe, but which cannot yet be detected despite over twenty years of intensive experimental attempts to do so?! As known the whole reason for hypothesizing the existence of these purely hypothetical "DM/DE" concepts – is the empirically validated accelerated expansion of the universe, i.e.: The "Hubble Tension" (Verde et al., 2023): there exists an "unexplained gap" between the earlier Cosmological measurements of the universe's expansion rate, and the higher contemporary measurements of an increased rate of the universe's expansion rate?! The current Astronomical Measurements of the universe's expansion rate is found to be: $H_0 = 73.0 \pm 1.0 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$ (SH0ES Collaboration; Riess et al. 2022); as opposed to the significantly lower rate of the universe's expansion obtained from an analysis of Planck observations of the cosmic microwave background (Planck Collaboration et al. 2020), predicting $H_0 = 67.4 \pm 0.5 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ together with the Λ CDM Model?!

The intriguing point is that even beyond the "troubling" fact that those purely hypothetical "DM/DE" concepts could not be verified experimentally (for the past twenty years)?! those purely hypothetical DM/DE concepts – may only be relevant for the (first) Hubble's Law, but not for the (second) "Hubble Tension" phenomenon. This is because even if (somehow) these purely hypothetical DM/DE concepts existed they could not explain an increase (over time) in the rate of the universe's expansion?! Rather, even if (somehow) there existed this "mysterious" and "elusive" DM/DE concepts, they could only account for a "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion (e.g., which does not change over time) – but not for the "Hubble Tension" validated "enigma" indicating an "unexplained" increase in the universe's expansion rate from its early Cosmological Measurement to the current (significantly increased) Astronomical measurement rate of

expansion over time?! Therefore, it is clear that the purely hypothetical stance of those DM/DE concepts (e.g., which could not be validated experimentally for over two full decades of intensive experimental efforts to do so?!), alongside its inability to account for the "Hubble Tension" enigma point at the "Paradigmatic Crisis" of the Old MCR Paradigm (together with the abovementioned "Theoretical Inconsistency" between GRT & QM)!

Nevertheless, according to Kuhn's analysis, whenever such a state of a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" appears in any given scientific discipline, it is followed by the discovery- and empirical validation- of a "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP), which is shown capable of satisfying a stringent list of scientific criteria, as follows:

- a) Shown capacity of this NSP to resolve the apparent "theoretical-inconsistency" found in the Old Standard Paradigm.
- b) Shown capacity of this NSP to replicate the major findings of the Old Standard Paradigm.
- 3) Identification of at least one (unique) "Critical Prediction" that can differentiate this NSP from the corresponding prediction/s of the Old Standard Paradigm.
- 4) To the extent that this (unique) "Critical Prediction" of the NSP is validated empirically to be more valid than the corresponding prediction of the Old Standard Paradigm – then this NSP has to be accepted as the New Paradigm (for that given scientific discipline)!

Fortunately, such a NSP has been discovered, termed: the "Computational Unified Field Theory" (CUFT), or recently called: "G-D's Physics" Fortunately, a new "Computational Unified Field Theory" (CUFT, recently also termed: "G-D's Physics") was discovered (Bentovish[1-30]), which was shown capable of satisfying these list of "stringent scientific criteria", including:

Resolving the (apparent) "Relativistic-Quantum Inconsistency": based on the discovery of a singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all "exhaustive spatial pixels" (in the universe) at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ (sec}^{-1}\text{)}$ " thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point"! The manner in which this New "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm was shown capable of resolving the (fundamental) "Relativistic-Quantum Inconsistency" is based on the UCP's new "computational definitions" of each of these Four Physical Features, which are based on the discovery of the UCP's two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" ("frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent"): wherein the UCP's computation of the UF's "frame" (level's) – "consistent" (e.g., "space") or "inconsistent" ("energy") Physical Features relates to the UCP's computation of the degree of "consistency" or "inconsistency" of any given object, relative to the entire UF's (frame of reference, e.g., across a series of UF's frame/s)! Or, conversely, the UCP's computation of any given object's "Object" (e.g., "internal-composition's) – "consistent" (e.g., "mass") or "inconsistent" (e.g., "time") produce the entire UF's exhaustive spatial pixels' Four basic Physical Features values!

The UCP's Four Physical Features (Novel) Computational Definitions:

"Space"

$S: (f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] + \dots f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$ such that: $f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n) \leq f_{\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} [UF's(i..n)]$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i..n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure! Conversely, the "en-

ergy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the.

"Energy"

E: $(f_i\{x,y,z\}[UF(i)] - \dots f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$
 such that: $f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)] > f_i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\} [UF's(i..n)]$
 wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's. In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes): $M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i..n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i..n)\}$ where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical): such that:

"Mass":

$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i..n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i..n)\}$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"Time":

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$T: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] \neq O(i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i..n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i..n)\}$ such that: $T: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i..n)] \leq c * h \{UF's(i..n)\}$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light. Universal Computational Formula (UCF):

FIGURE 1: UCP'S COMPUTATION OF FOUR PHYSICAL FEATURES

Framework/Consist.	Frame	Object
Consistent	"Space"	"Mass"
Inconsistent	"Energy"	"Time"

Additionally, "G-D's Physics" resolution of the apparent "Relativistic-Quantum Inconsistency" is based on the realization that this UCP simultaneously computes: "Single Spatial-Temporal" (SST), "Multiple

Spatial-Temporal" (MST) and "Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal" (EST) types of computation, giving rise to increasingly more "exhaustive" forms of computation that integrate (and indeed resolve) this apparent "Relativistic-Quantum Inconsistency":

According to this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, the (alternative) explanation- and "resolution" - of this apparent "GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency" stems from the UCP's simultaneous (singular higher-ordered) computation of all "Single Spatial-Temporal" computation ("SST"): subatomic "particle" or "relativistic object" – i.e., relating to only "one" spatial-temporal point, at any given moment; "Multi Spatial-Temporal" computation (MST): (subatomic) "wave" – i.e., relating to at least "two" points being measured at any point in time; or "Exhaustive Spatial Temporal" (EST) computation – i.e., relating to all "exhaustive" spatial pixels comprising an entire "Universal Frame"! (Figure 3);

FIGURE 2: UCP'S "SST", "MST" & "EST" COMPUTATIONS

UCP's Computations	SST	MST	EST
Num. "ST" Points	1	2+	All Points

The manner in which "G-D's Physics" new theoretical conceptualization conceives of the UCP's computation of those Four basic Physical Features, as well as of its simultaneous computation of SST, MST and EST values – allows for a complete integration of Relativistic and Quantum Models, based on the discovery of the UCP's singular "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF):

FIGURE 3: The "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\begin{matrix}
 \uparrow \\
 \left. \begin{matrix} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{matrix} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m} \\
 \downarrow \\
 \text{UF's } \{n...n...x\} [Px] (a...z)
 \end{matrix}$$

Note: which is accompanied by "G-D'S PHYSICS" computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time".

Wherein the UCP represented by the Hebrew Letter " , " computes at an extremely rapid rate, e.g., of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ (sec') simultaneously every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising every consecutive UF's – including the UCP's complete integration of those Four basic Physical Features through the UCF's: s * e / t * m computation (e.g., for each exhaustive spatial pixel – from "a to z")! Indeed, in over 120 (peer-reviewed) scientific articles published regarding this New "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm, an elaboration of the manner in which this UCP computes each consecutive UF's, i.e., based on its Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD's) has been given.

However, relevant to our discussion of the manner in which "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm is capable of resolving the Relativistic-Quantum Inconsistency is the understanding that it includes and integrates those Four basic Physical Features as "secondary computational by-products" of the UCP's singular computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby also replicating and integrating all major Relativistic and Quantum laws and phenomena! This can be glanced also from the two "Relativistic Format" and "Quantum Format" of the (singular) UCF:

The UCF's Relativistic Format:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \text{,} \\ \text{E} * \underline{s} \\ \text{t} \end{array} \right\} = \left. \begin{array}{l} \underline{M * c^2} \\ \text{h} \end{array} \right\}$$

in which GRT's (famous) "Energy-Mass Equivalence" is embedded within the UCF.

The UCF's Quantum Format:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \text{,} \\ \underline{t * m} \\ \text{c}^2 \end{array} \right\} = \left. \begin{array}{l} \underline{s * e * h *} \\ \text{c}^2 \end{array} \right\}$$

in which "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" ("complimentary pairs") are embedded as "special cases" within the UCF (see previously elaborated analysis of "G-D'S PHYSICS").

Interestingly, this (latter) new "G-D's Physics" UCP's (,) computation of the UCF's "Quantum Format" clearly reveals a much "deeper" understanding of the basic "computational constraint" imposed by Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" that stems from "G-D's Physics" singular higher-ordered UCP's simultaneous computation of those Four (basic) Physical Features (for all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe) – rather than as "caused" by any (direct) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two subatomic) "probe" and "target" elements; which serves as the current QM's "theoretical explanation" for Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" (e.g., and associated assumed "collapse" of the "target's probability wave-function" – as "caused" by this direct "material-causal" physical interaction between the subatomic probe and target elements)!? This is because if we realize that according to "G-D's Physics" (novel) UCP's computational definitions of these Four basic Physical Features (above) – arising from the four possible combinations of the two Computational Dimensions: "Framework" ("frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent"): "Frame" – "consistent" (e.g., "space") or "inconsistent" (e.g., "energy"), and "Object" – "consistent" (e.g., "mass") or "inconsistent" ("time")! Then, we can immediately see that the real "*intrinsic computational-complimentary*" reason for Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" is not any direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between the subatomic "probe" and "target's" (assumed "prob-

ability wave function") elements! But rather, this "UCP's intrinsic computational complementarity" is the real reason for Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" stems from the "UCP's *intrinsic computational complementarity*": i.e., since the UCP simultaneously computes both the "Framework" – "consistent" ("space") and "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") and "inconsistent" ("time") values of any given object (e.g., exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – at the incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec), therefore any increase in the accuracy level of the measurement of any one of these "UCP's computational pairs", i.e., "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") necessarily leads to a proportional decrease in the other "UCP's computational pair's" accuracy level!

Moreover, since this singular (higher-ordered) UCP simultaneously computes all Four Physical Features (for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising each consecutive UF's frame/s), therefore the singular "Universal Computational Formula" completely integrates (e.g., for the first time in Physics!) those Four Physical Features as "secondary computational by-products" of the same singular (higher-ordered) UCP computation! Indeed, as can be seen from the two (abovementioned) "Relativistic" and "Quantum" Formats of this singular UCF, we can see that "G-D's Physics" novel UCF completely integrates – not only between those Four basic Physical Features, but also completely integrates GRT & QM as "special cases" within this broader and (indeed) exhaustive new theoretical framework! Hence, not only do those key Relativistic "Energy-Mass Equivalence" ("E = Mc²") and Quantum's Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" (e.g., stemming not from any direct "material-causal" physical interaction between the subatomic "probe" and "target" elements, but is rather due to the "UCP's intrinsic computational complementarity"!)) being embedded within the singular UCF's Relativistic and Quantum Formats, but more broadly, its been previously shown that all key Relativistic and Quantum phenomena and laws are being replicated (and indeed "transcended" as merely representing "special cases" within "G-D's Physics" more exhaustive theoretical framework).

Indeed, if at least one such (unique) "Critical Prediction" of the New CUFT Paradigm is verified as "more valid" than the corresponding predictions of the Old Paradigm's GRT's & QM's predictions – then (according to Kuhn's 31 well accepted analysis) that particular scientific discipline (e.g., in our case Theoretical Physics) has to accept the New CUFT as the New (satisfactory) Physics Paradigm (for the Twenty-First Century)! Indeed, we've been blessed with such an identification of two such (unique) "Critical Predictions" of CUFT New Scientific Paradigm – which are being shown to be "more valid" than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, therefore leading to the unequivocal acceptance of CUFT as the New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

Materials & Methods

In order to directly contrast between the new "G-D'S PHYSICS" Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-D'S PHYSICS" identified two unique "Critical-Prediction" relating to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in Its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) due to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" (CHCFH) associated with the two days "Rosh-Hashanah" (New Year's) time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCP; According to the Old ("Material-Causal") GRT's Paradigm, the (purely hypothetical concept of) DM predicts a "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion – i.e., which should not increase over time! In contrast, according to one of the new Theoretical Postulates of the "G-D'S PHYSICS" termed: "The Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" (CHCFH), whenever there is a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF), e.g., of a large group of human-beings focusing upon this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), this results in an "Uni-

verse's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion ("UNCIARE")! For example, during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana's" (new year) two days' special time-interval, according to the CUFT (unique) "UNCIARE-JRH" "Critical Prediction", there should be measured a "non-continuous increase" in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., predicted to occur during the JRH's two days special annual interval of a CHCF!)

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction

Pohl et al.[54-56] set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum\{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i...n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i...n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Results

Indeed, the "Hubble's Tension"[32-35] points at a more specific "CAGUARE" increase in the universe's expansion rate (across time) – from the universe's initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion [32-35]?! In other words, the unique CAGUARE "Critical Prediction", predicting that the Universe's expansion rate will increase (annually) during every consecutive JRH's two days' (special) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – is validated by the "Hubble's Tension"[32-35] findings! In contrast, these "Hubble's Tension"[32-35] findings cannot be explained by the current "Standard Material-Causal" Paradigm of GRT, which assumes that the universe's accelerated expansion is the result of (purely hypothetical) "Dark Matter" concepts, which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe (but which failed to be detected despite twenty years of intensive experimentation attempting to do so)!? Even beyond that, even theoretically this (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" concept could not account for the empirically observed "Hubble's Tension"[32-35] because such a (purely hypothetical) DM concept could only account for a constant-rate expansion of the universe (e.g., over time), but not for the "Hubble's Tension"32-35 CAGUARE results indicating that the universe's rate of expansion increases over time!? Therefore, we see that the "Hubble's Tension"[32-35] (otherwise "unexplained") empirical results unequivocally support "G-D's Physics"

unique CAGUARE Critical Prediction!

Likewise, the empirically measured "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings precisely support "G-D's Physics" novel UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given particle as function of its "Object Spatial Consistency" (across a series of UF's Frames); therefore the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the (relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen") than the (relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen") was predicted by "G-D's Physics" to lead to a "spatially-smaller"- and spatially more accurate"- measurement of that "Muon-Hyde" empirical findings! In contrast, these "Proton-Radius Puzzle" empirical findings could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force"⁴⁹, interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction^{53,57}, higher dimension gravity⁴⁸, a new boson⁵², and the quasi-free hypothesis $\pi+51$; and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm! Hence, these "Proton-Radius Puzzle" empirical results unequivocally support "G-D's Physics" unique Critical Prediction stemming from its (novel) UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given (subatomic) particle (or relativistic object)!

Taken together, these results unequivocally support two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old (Standard) "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, thereby substantiating this New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm as the New Physics Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

Discussion

Based on this (unequivocal) empirical validation of the CUFT's unique UNCIARE-JRH "Critical Prediction", as more valid than the corresponding (purely hypothetical) DM-predicted "constant rate" of the universe's expansion, Science must accept this CUFT as the New (valid) 21st Century Physics Paradigm! It resolves: a) The basic "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM based on the discovery of the singular (higher-ordered) UCP which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe: i.e., including all "Single Spatial-Temporal" (e.g., "SST") "Multiple Spatial-Temporal" ("MST"), and even "Exhaustive Spatial Temporal" UCP's computations (as delineated previously) b) "Hubble's Tension"32-35: based on the CUFT's postulated "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) two days' (special) JRH's UNCIARE in the universe's expansion rate – validated through the CUFT's predicted UNCIARE (JRH) "CAGUARE" (otherwise "unexplained") phenomenon! c) The CUFT's discarding of the purely hypothetical DM concept as "superfluous" (or "non-existent")!?

Finally, the acceptance of this (novel) CUFT as the New Twenty-First Century Physics Paradigm significantly advances our scientific understanding of the true "origin", "age", "sustenance" and "development" of the universe (recently) announcing the "Seven Months Astronomers' Challenge" based on a much greater precision measurement of this UNCIARE-JRH accurate value of the UNCIARE-JRH predicted increase in the universe's (annual) expansion rate! A "G-D's Physics' Seven Months' Challenge (for Astronomers all of the world!) to validate its direct UNCIARE-JRH's increase in the current Astronomical Measure of the universe's expansion rate (i.e., to be measured during the next seven months at an accuracy level of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc) by a "Minute Annual Increase" (MAI) of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc: that will occur on the next JRH, on Oct. 3rd-4th, 2024 (and carry on until the next JRH: Sep. 22nd-23rd, 2025 – in which another MAI of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc will be added to the universe's accelerated rate of expansion!) To the extent that this specific "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH MAI (of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc) will be validated empirically then this will unequivocally validate "G-D's Physics" whole new theoret-

ical model wherein a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) that have been "pre-planned" to "steer" the universe from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State": in which Science & Humanity recognize the singularity of this UCP, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony", which will also characterize Humanity's state of existence (which is currently beginning with the acceptance of "G-D's Physics" as the New 21st Century Scientific Paradigm)!

It therefore seems that the current empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) as the New Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics represents a major and fundamental advancement in our basic understanding of the true "origin" - "sustenance" and even "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" of the entire physical universe!

"G-D's Physics" Centrality of the Earth's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" in the Universe!

One of the key differences between the New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm and the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm is the "Centrality of Human Consciousness" - i.e., in "space" and "time", and its intimate connection with the "Universal Consciousness Reality's" (UCR's) "Geulah Driven Universe" (GDU)! This is because according to "G-D's Physics" New (empirically proven) Scientific Paradigm, it seems that "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) plays a major role in the "Universe's Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE)! As we've already seen, there is clear (and direct) empirical evidence for the centrality of this CHCF in terms of its UNCIARE's acceleration in the universe! As outlined above, in contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" concept (e.g., which has been negated both based on the experimental failure to detect its existence experimentally, and "G-D's Physics" principle computational negation of its associated Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's SRCS Computational Structure!) - which assumes that this (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" concept can only account for a "constant-rate" expansion rate of the universe; the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm points at an increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, e.g., "UNCIARE" due to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", which occurs during the Jewish Rosh Hashanah's (two days' special) time-interval!

Indeed, it has been proven empirically (above) that it is solely based on this CHCF that the universe's rate of expansion "increases over time", e.g., as indicated by the (otherwise unexplained) "Universe's Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UCAGUARE)!; An even more direct (further) validation of the centrality of the CHCF was called for Astronomers to validate during the upcoming two days' Jewish Rosh Hashanah - during Oct. 3-4, 2024, in which it is predicted that the universe's rate of expansion will significantly increase (and continue to increase) during the whole ensuing Jewish year), relative to the universe's measured rate of expansion in the preceding time prior to Oct. 3-4, 2024! Moreover, previously it's been shown that this same CHCF may be responsible for the Centrality of Human Consciousness - not just in "time" but also in "space"! This relates to the otherwise "unexplained" empirically validated phenomenon wherein the Astronomical measurement of the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion (UARE) also indicates that planet Earth stands at the center of this UARE! In other words, it may be the case wherein the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion - i.e., related to "space", wherein it is only relative to planet Earth's position that this accelerated rate of expansion pertaining to the furthest regions of space (wherein the farther any galactic element exists relative to planet Earth the faster its measured acceleration would be)! If (for instance) it is

found that such equivalent Astronomical measurements of the UARE - do not yield the same "symmetrical increase" in the universe's UARE then this would validate the centrality of planet Earth (and its associated centrality of this CHCF) - in "space", as well as in "time"!

The alternative (novel) explanation offered by the New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- and development- of the whole physical universe is solely based on the operation of the singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) that (solely) exists both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely responsible for the computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"!); And specifically, as associated with this UCP's connection with the CHCF - which brings about the UCP's initiation of the UNCIARE (empirically validated) phenomenon! In other words, the UNCIARE empirically validated phenomenon (unequivocally) proves that the origination of the entire physical universe, and its accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., as indicated by the "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion", CAGUARE) is brought about by the UCP's consecutive computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s - and specifically by the CHCF's UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, e.g., assumed to take place at every Annual "Jewish Rosh-Hashanah" two days' time-interval (i.e., this year this will take place during Oct. 3-4, 2024 and onwards in which it is predicted the rate of the universe's expansion will increase significantly, relative to the rate of the universe's expansion prior to the Oct. 3-4, 2024 - which I've called Astronomers and Cosmologists to test experimentally!) Indeed, once we realize that the entire physical universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s and that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s; and therefore that the only "force" that creates- "dissolves"- re-creates- and evolves- any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe is this singular higher-ordered UCP; hence, based on the clear empirical evidence indicating an UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe's expansion associated with the CHCF (hypothesized to take place during the Jew Rosh Hashanah!) we reach the inevitable theoretical conclusion wherein the expansion of the entire physical universe depends upon the CHCF - which brings about this UNCIARE increase in the universe's expansion rate (beginning in each Jewish Rosh Hashanah and continuing throughout the entire subsequent Jewish Year).

Hence, based upon the fulfillment of these (stringent) necessary conditions for the acceptance of "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) - points at "G-D's Physics" as the New (valid) Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century! It is important to note that this New "G-D's Physics" was shown to resolve the apparent "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM - and in fact unify between them based on its discovery of the (novel) "Universal Computational Formula", which was also shown to unify (for the first time in Theoretical Physics) between the Four basic Physical Features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"), as well as between the Four Forces! Nevertheless, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm was characterized as an "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, stemming from its discovery of the singular (higher-ordered) UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frames (back into the singularity of the UCP)! According to this New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's frame/s! This profound new discovery made by the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm principally negates some of the most basic assumptions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, including: GRT's "Big-Bang Model" and the existence of any purely hypothetical "dark-matter" concept (as the as-

sumed "caused" for the accelerated expansion of the physical universe, as explained above).

Instead, "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (empirically validated) Scientific Paradigm has been shown to point at the fact that the whole origination- sustenance- "dissolution"- and development of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as its entirety) has been "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP to evolve the universe from its initial "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" in which Humanity and Science will recognize the singularity of this "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) or "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), which is also characterized by Humanity's (and Science's) "embracing" of this singular UCP's/UCR's intrinsic properties of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony"! Thus, the New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm explains the whole origination- sustenance- ("dissolution"-) and development- of the entire physical universe: not as created by an initial "random" "Big-Bang" nuclear event, and the whole development of the universe – as leading to an ("inevitable") "dissipation" (e.g., based on the Second Law of Thermodynamics), which was shown to be negated by "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm and its CDP); but rather as being "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR for the fulfillment of the universe's "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" (e.g., Morally, Spiritually and even Physically!

"G-D's Physics" Resolution of the "Hubble's-Tension" Enigma!

Indeed, the direct empirical validation of two (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as being more valid (or accurate) than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM substantiate "G-D's Physics" as the New (valid) Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm! But, even beyond that, the acceptance of "G-D's Physics" New 21st Century Scientific Paradigm also potentially resolves the "Hubble's Tension" Enigma by offering an alternative (coherent novel) theoretical model that sheds a completely "new light" explicating the true dynamics underlying what seems as an otherwise "unexplained" "Hubble's Tension" Enigma! This is because according to the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm's assumption wherein the universe was created by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, and that its accelerated rate of expansion is "caused" by purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" (which is assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe, but which failed to be detected even after twenty years of intensive experimentations trying to detect this "elusive" purely hypothetical DM); according to this MCR assumption there cannot be any viable explanation for Hubble's Tension³²⁻³⁵, e.g., the unexplained "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Rate of Expansion"; because even if this (purely hypothetical – and experimentally undetected) "DM" (somehow) existed – it could not account (or explain) the increase in the universe's rate of expansion from its early "Background Radiation" Cosmological value to the current (e.g., significantly increased) Astronomical value!? In contrast, since the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm negates the very possibility of the existence of any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" (random) physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing either in the "same" or even "different" UF's frame/s due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s back into the singularity of this UCP?! therefore, as we've seen this New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm (principally) negated the existence of such a "material-causal" (initial) "Big-Bang" nuclear event, as well as negated the possibility of the existence of such (purely hypothetical) "DM" element – because (once again) there could not exist any such "material-causal" (direct or indirect) physical interactions between

such (purely hypothetical) DM element and any "galactic elements, e.g., "causing" their expulsion etc.!!

Instead, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm stipulates that the whole (continuous) "origination"- "dissolution"- "re-creation"- and "development"- of every exhaustive spatial in the universe (as well as its entirety) is totally dependent upon the continuous computation of this singular higher-ordered UCP of every consecutive UF's frame/s (at the incredible rate of " c^2/h " = $1.36 \cdot 10^{50}$ sec!) Moreover, as outlined above (and previously) since this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computation/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) is characterized by such "sublime" characteristics as "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" – and has (in fact) "pre-planned" the whole development of the universe from its "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals, and human-beings: all leading up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP and those "sublime characteristics", which will therefore also characterized Humanity's "Geulah Perfected State" (in which there will be no violence and aggression, wars or conflicts – instead Humanity existing in a state of "Peace & Harmony" etc.) Hence, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm has discovered the "special role" that Humanity plays in this UCP's "pre-planned" development of the entire physical universe: not only in "steering" the whole ("pre-planned") development of the universe to lead up to that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of Humanity (and the universe); but also according to "G-D's Physics" stipulated "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF), the occurrence of such CHCF, e.g., such as during the two-days' time-interval of the Jewish Rosh Hashana (JRH: this year occurring on the 3rd-4th of October, 2024) brings about an "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE-JRH)! Indeed, this implies that according to "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH (unique) "Critical Prediction", cumulatively, this (annual) UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's expansion rate could lead to the empirically observed "Hubble's-Tension" (e.g., or as "G-D's Physics" terms it as the "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion, "CAGAURE" phenomenon)!

Indeed, a potentially far-reaching theoretical implication – and additional (unique) "Critical Prediction" ensuing from "G-D's Physics" postulated CHCF relates to the computation of the precise* Astronomical measurement of UNCIARE-JRH's Critical Prediction of an increase in the current Astronomical Value of the Universe's Expansion Rate, i.e., by a "Minute Annual Increase" (MAI) of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc that will occur in the upcoming JRH: Oct. 3rd -4th, 2024, relative to such MAI* (precision measurement sensitivity) of the current rate of the universe's expansion (and will carry through until the next JRH: Sep. 22nd-23rd, 2025 – in which another MAI of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc will be added to the universe's accelerated rate of expansion!)*This MAI computation is derived from "G-D's Physics" cumulative CHCF computation. Indeed, there is a current Call for Astronomers to validate this unique "UNCIARE-JRH" Critical Prediction (e.g., including its specific *MAI value increase etc. delineated) **through RJMP's current Announcement (above): "AN INTERNATIONAL CONTEST FOR VALIDATION OF 'G-D'S PHYSICS' 'UNCIARE-JRH' CRITICAL PREDICTION & RESOLUTION OF THE 'HUBBLE'S TENSION' ENIGMA!"**

Dedication

This article I dedicated to my dear beloved (diseased) Mother, Dr. Tirzah Bentwich, (Tirzah Bat Yitzchak) in association with her "Yahrzeit" passing date, ד' תמוז (for her upliftment).

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